

<https://doi.org/10.1038/s44383-026-00028-6>

The grapevine as a model plant to describe intra- and interspecific mechanisms of drought acclimation

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Grapevines acclimate to water stress primarily through a combination of stress-avoidance and stress-tolerance mechanisms. From this perspective, we revisit the potential interactions between grapevine scions and rootstocks under drought, emphasizing their specificities across a broad biological space spanning both intra- and inter-*Vitis* diversity as well as their associated microbiomes. Building on the described ecophysiological responses, we summarize the main known biomolecular adjustments and their potential applications in assisted breeding programmes.

Main text

The wine grapevine (*Vitis vinifera* L.) originated in the Middle East, was domesticated in the Mediterranean basin and in Europe, and only more recently expanded into the New Worlds. In each of these regions it encountered different climates¹, cultivation systems, soils and winemaking traditions². Its ability to adapt to such diverse growing conditions was made possible by an immense intraspecific biodiversity, which has produced hundreds of cultivars selected in different environments. Moreover, to protect vines from phylloxera, *V. vinifera* has been systematically grafted for more than a century onto rootstocks belonging to other *Vitis* species, either monospecific or, more commonly, hybrids resulting from interspecific crossbreeding³.

Across this wide biological landscape, grapevines display a full spectrum of drought-acclimation strategies, ranging from extreme stress tolerance to stress avoidance, in which the water status of the plant regulates the transpiration possibilities, and vice versa⁴. This interplay has direct consequences for carbon assimilation and primary metabolism, both under drought and during subsequent rehydration⁵. It also has indirect effects on secondary metabolism, mediated by well-characterized hormonal balances, particularly abscisic acid (ABA)⁶. Because secondary metabolism of the berry underlies key viticultural goals and ultimately determines oenological success (or failure), the specific mechanism linking drought resistance to the ripening process have been extensively investigated and clarified over the years⁷.

Strategies available to deal with water shortage

Grapevines can employ multiple strategies to cope with water stress, centred on two main and apparently antithetical mechanisms: avoidance (primarily through stomatal closure) and tolerance (mainly via

osmoregulation and the control of xylem embolism)⁸. The strategy, or combination of strategies, adopted is largely determined by its evolutionary adaptation to environments with limited water availability. However, additional factors, such as soil type, intensity and rate of stress development, and the presence or memory of previous stress episodes, can further modulate the strategic shift of individual plants toward avoidance or tolerance⁴.

In theory, a fully successful, strict drought-avoidance strategy leads the vine to regulate stomatal opening from the very first days of water shortage. An effective reduction in stomatal conductance (g_s), driven either by a root-to-shoot ABA signal or by the redistribution of ABA within the leaves, progressively limits transpiration losses, even under high demand (high air vapour pressure deficit, VPD). This enables the plant to maintain a stable leaf water status, i.e. a perfect (but theoretical) isohydric response to stress (Fig. 1a).

Conversely, a complete failure of stomatal control would immediately trigger tolerance mechanisms. As water potential declines, the plant activates countermeasures such as osmotic adjustment and repair of xylem embolisms, formed due to the increasingly negative potentials and associated xylem tension. In this *scenario*, at least theoretically, stomatal regulation plays essentially no role; instead, the vine relies on the osmotic responses to endure stress. This represents true tolerance to progressive water deficit, with the water status of the plant shifting drastically from day to day: a fully anisohydric response (Fig. 1b).

Osmoprotective responses typical of low water potential can arise either from environmental scarcity of available water, or, conversely, from excessive transpiration. The latter occurs in plants with inefficient stomatal control, which continue to transpire abundantly despite the onset of water stress.

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Fig. 1 | Theoretical kinetics of stomatal conductance (g_s) and leaf water potential (Ψ_{leaf}) over 10 days of absence of water supply under optimal transpiration conditions. **a from day 2 to day 11 the grapevine exhibits a response dominated by stomatal control, which allows to maintain an isohydric leaf status (stable midday Ψ_{leaf} and slight progressive decline in the predawn values). This is the theoretical**

representation of a pure drought avoidance response. **b** from day 2 to day 11 the plant shows a progressive activation of osmotic adjustment, leading to lower midday Ψ_{leaf} , sustained transpirational dissipation, and a pronounced reduction in predawn Ψ_{leaf} , reflecting the gradual depletion of soil water. This is the theoretical representation of a pure drought tolerance response.

In grapevine, these two behaviours have not evolved as mutually exclusive but rather as coexisting strategies. The broad platform provided by cultivars and rootstocks adapted to diverse climates has produced a continuous gradient between avoidance and tolerance mechanisms⁹. By plotting the maximum g_s values and the minimum daily leaf water potential (midday Ψ_{leaf}) over the ten days of the incipient-drought kinetics described in Fig. 1, it becomes possible to visualize this *continuum*. On one end lies a strictly 'vertical' response, representing the theoretical response of complete avoidance and a purely isohydric behaviour (days 2i–11i). On the opposite end is a strictly 'horizontal' response, fully tolerant of continuous transpirative dissipation, corresponding to a purely anisohydric behaviour (days 2a–11a) (Fig. 2). In a meta-analysis describing the factors governing stomatal conductance in relation to water availability⁴, real-world behaviours consistently fall between these two extremes: more vertical when the plant is more evasive (i.e. a stress avoider), and more horizontal when it is more tolerant.

Main mechanisms controlling water stress avoidance in grapevine

The definitive mechanism for avoiding water stress is stomatal closure. For decades, grapevine has served as a strong model for how stomatal control is regulated through both ABA-mediated and hydraulic factors¹⁰. The ABA pathway exemplifies *i*) root-to-shoot signalling via the xylem, *ii*) chemical modulation of hormonal signals, *iii*) foliar regulation of signal intensity, and *iv*) stomatal sensitivity to the transmitted signal.

- i. The root biosynthesizes ABA when its water potential declines, that is, when water in the soil, and therefore at the soil-root interface, becomes progressively less available¹¹. Rootstocks that strongly induce stomatal closure synthesize ABA at less negative potentials than those associated with anisohydric regulation (tolerant rootstocks, see next paragraph). Soil water availability certainly depends on its absolute quantity, which underlies both the historical associations between grapevine cultivars and their native rainfalls regimes, and the principles of irrigation scheduling in hot, arid environments¹². However, availability also depends on soil nature and texture. After rainfall or irrigation, clay-rich soils often exhibit

lower water availability (and thus lower water potential of the soil-plant system) because fine particles retain water strongly through matrix components¹³. Yet as drought progresses, this pattern reverses: clay-rich soils retain more water for longer, whereas sandy soils rapidly lose water to plant transpiration, evaporation from the soil surface, and gravitational demands at depth¹⁴. At this stage, the water potential experienced by roots in predominantly sandy soils is more negative than in fine-textured soils, thereby increasing root ABA biosynthesis. In all cases, the ABA synthesized in roots is transported in the xylem stream toward the leaves, driven by transpiration¹⁵. Interestingly, this root-derived ABA signal forms the theoretical and experimental foundation for numerous split-root studies in grapevine, particularly those inspired by the work of Brian Loveys, Peter Dry and colleagues, who introduced the partial root drying (PRD) technique in grapevine¹⁶.

- ii. The activity of the root-derived hormonal signal is conditioned by the pH of the xylem sap¹⁷. A sub-acidic sap, reflecting effective protonation of the root apoplast (i.e., high respiratory activity), attenuates the signal by protonating the free negative valences of ABA (a weakly dissociated acid). Conversely, when the sap is subalkaline, indicating reduced root ATPase activity, the limited availability of apoplastic hydrogen ions prevents attenuation of the ABA⁺ signal, thereby maximizing its effectiveness in triggering stomatal closure. This provides a clear example of how variations in root respiration can regulate stomatal activity.
- iii. The activity of mesophyll cells, through the production of photosynthetic ATP, can also modulate the ABA signal. The mechanism mirrors that in the roots: higher ATPase activity leads to stronger apoplastic protonation (acidification), which in turn attenuates the ABA signal.
- iv. Finally, when ABA reaches its receptors on guard cells and triggers the signalling cascade for stomatal closure, cultivar-specific differences in receptor sensitivity come into play. Cultivars with a predominantly isohydric response, the clearest representatives of drought-avoidance behaviour, tend to be highly sensitive to the ABA signal¹⁸, and this sensitivity must reside in the properties and function of the ABA receptors in guard cells.

Fig. 2 | Interrelationship between maximum daily stomatal conductance (g_s) and corresponding minimum leaf water potential (midday ψ_{leaf}). The plot illustrates the two theoretical extremes: a pure ‘vertical’ response, representing complete drought avoidance and strictly isohydric behaviour (days 2–11, 2i–11i, red empty squares), in contrast with a pure ‘horizontal’ response, totally tolerant of continuous transpiration dissipation and descriptive of a strictly anisohydric behaviour (days

2–11, 2a–11a, red crosses). Intermediate situations between the two theoretical extremes are modelled to represent real cases, based on a meta-analysis of 718 data points from 26 different *Vitis vinifera* varieties investigated as scions, 15 non-*V. vinifera* rootstock genotypes and 11 own-rooted *V. vinifera* varieties. Linearised data were analysed using the univariate general linear model (GLM), following Lavoie-Lamoureux et al.⁴

In addition, other root-to-shoot signals complementary and synergistic to the ABA signal have been identified in grapevine, through exchange of miRNAs¹⁹ or small peptides²⁰.

Conversely, in hydraulic mechanisms, the turgor-driven water status of guard cells overrides hormonal signalling. In this case, stomatal regulation is linked to the declining leaf water potential, which may result from limited soil water availability, limited root absorption capacity, and/or xylem systems with low hydraulic conductivity (e.g. high incidence of embolism). The drop in leaf water potential also triggers local ABA biosynthesis, which supports stomatal closure long after the initial hydraulic signal²¹. This hydraulic signal, which directly induces stomatal closure, will be discussed further in the next section. When stomata close, reduced transpiration helps conserve water, but the evaporative cooling system of the plant (its only mechanism for heat dissipation) loses effectiveness. As a result, severe water stress accompanied by prolonged stomatal closure causes physiological dysfunction due to leaf overheating. In many wine-growing regions worldwide, water stress thus leads to heat stress²², also because arid environments are often simultaneously hot²³. How does the vine defend itself? The response involves a complex interplay of photorespiration and photoinhibition. In short: high temperatures in the chloroplast shift Rubisco activity toward oxygenation rather than carboxylation. This means the diversion of ribulose-6-phosphate into C2 compounds that enter the photorespiratory pathway, instead of C3 intermediates used for the biosynthesis of primary sugars in the Calvin-Benson cycle. Photorespiration consumes ATP and dissipates excess energy, an important function when high light adds to heat. Since the sun is the source of both heat and light, photorespiration acts as a safety mechanism protecting the leaf from photoinhibition (often irreversible). Protection against photoinhibition also relies on photoprotective and antioxidant systems. Under excessive radiation, water photolysis shifts from the production of more stable molecular oxygen (O_2) to generating reactive oxygen species (ROS), chemical intermediates between water and O_2 . The link between photoprotective defence and the biosynthesis of photooxidative target molecules (mainly polyphenols) is the

key to the success of many grape- and wine-quality outcomes. This is especially relevant when ROS generated in leaves are phloem-translocated to berries during ripening. Similarly, ABA in leaves and fruits promotes the biosynthesis of secondary metabolites²⁴. For these reasons, grapevine is a leading model plant for studying the coordination between stress responses and fruit ripening processes^{7,25}.

At the root level, ABA plays an important role in shaping root system architecture, by integrating root branching control with the recruitment of beneficial microorganisms. High root ABA production also correlates with efficient root deepening: ABA stimulates the elongation of primary roots while restricting lateral root formation and improving root hydraulic properties²⁶ (Fig. 3).

Main mechanisms controlling water stress tolerance in grapevine

When stomatal control is not strict, the vine continues to transpire for an extended time even under suboptimal water availability. Rootstocks with low ABA production and/or cultivars with low ABA sensitivity are responsible for this phenomenon, which underlies anisohydric responses to water stress. In general, rootstocks that promote this response tend to increase plant vigour, especially when water availability is high²⁷. These are genuinely drought-tolerant rootstocks, often derived from hybrids with *Vitis rupestris*^{28,29}. They exhibit strong branching, hydraulic vulnerability segmentation, and good soil-exploration capacity. Most importantly, they are able to osmoregulate and adjust aquaporin function to maintain cell viability as water potential drops, since the reduction in soil water availability is not offset by effective stomatal regulation^{30,31}. In arid environments, such rootstocks help maintain functional physiological activity over prolonged dry periods. However, when paired with tolerant cultivars, they may require emergency irrigation to prevent irreversible damage if leaf water potential becomes too low (around -1.5 , -2.0 MPa at midday).

The basis of tolerance therefore lies in the osmoregulatory capacity of both the root system and the above-ground portions of the plant. However,

Fig. 3 | Schematic summary of the main strategies for grapevine acclimation to water stress. This diagram illustrates contrasting isohydric (stress avoidance) and anisohydric (stress tolerance) mechanisms. Isohydric genotypes rely on rapid ABA biosynthesis, ABA/pH regulation, and stomatal closure to conserve water, with soil texture strongly influencing signal intensity. In contrast, anisohydric genotypes

sustain transpiration under declining water potentials, relying on hydraulic signalling, osmotic adjustment, aquaporin activity, and embolism recovery. Differences in ABA sensitivity and metabolite accumulation highlight how genotype, soil conditions, and physiological trade-offs collectively shape drought acclimation and underpin grapevine’s role as a model for perennial crops.

tolerance strategies correlate with deep reductions in water potential along the root-stem-leaf axis, which in turn promote xylem embolism. Grapevine has long been studied as a model species for understanding the control of xylem embolism⁶. Both passive resistance to embolism formation and efficient embolism repair have been suggested as key factors controlling anisohydric response behaviour (i.e., drought tolerance). In general, vessels with smaller diameters are less prone to embolism, whereas larger vessels, because of their greater lumen area and volume, are more susceptible to air seeding and bubble formation, processes that ultimately lead to embolization³². Recently, however, calls have been made for a more nuanced assessment of the vessel diameter-vulnerability relationship, to gain a better mechanistic understanding of the nanoscale biophysical processes that drive embolism initiation and spread^{33,34}. This issue is particularly important in vineyard research, where a progressive acclimation to embolism is observed as the growing season advances³⁵.

Much of the literature on rootstocks and scions examines the anatomy of the xylem system, drawing on both traditional microscopic analyses and,

more recently, on X-ray tomographic measurements (micro-CT)³⁶. Furthermore, in grapevine, embolism recovery in the late afternoon or at night has been described as a common and effective mechanism³⁷. Thus, biological control of the hydraulic system does not depend solely on avoiding embolism formation (which results from declining water potential and increasing hydrostatic tension in the xylem), but also on the ability to repair embolized vessels. Embolism recovery is based on two concurrent processes. The first is the transfer of osmoregulatory sugars from the phloem into the xylem, which draws water from the perivascular cells and the apoplast back into the embolized conduits. Recent studies have proposed a role for non-structural carbohydrates (NSCs) in generating the osmotic pressure required for refilling^{38,39}. Moreover, different cultivars appear to adopt distinct NSC-use strategies during drought: in ‘Grenache’, sucrose accumulation is closely associated with embolism formation and may help sustain refilling; in ‘Barbera’, NSCs may contribute to a conduit-recovery strategy via the formation of cell-wall hydrogels, which likely explain the reduction of conduit lumen detected by micro-CT⁴⁰. The second phenomenon involves

the regulation of membrane aquaporins in perivascular cells, which increases cell permeability and accelerates water movement during the recovery phases of xylem embolism⁴¹. In rootstocks derived from *Vitis rupestris*, this aquaporin-mediated activity is closely associated with successful recovery from embolisms²⁸.

The decrease in water potential that triggers tolerance mechanisms also serves as an important signal for stomatal closure, as mentioned in the previous section. In this case, roots transmit hydraulic signals upward (decreasing the water potential of the entire plant system), while ABA can be synthesized locally in the leaves⁴². This makes it impossible to frame grapevine behaviour within a strict binary of isohydry *versus* anisohydry, as recently unequivocally demonstrated on 30 own-rooted winegrape cultivars originating from different European regions, tested in the same investigation site by Obiero and Keller⁴³. Instead, stomatal control can be activated following a drop in water potential, with different vine species or cultivars responding more or less readily also depending on their genetics, rootstock and soil type⁴.

The plant hydraulic system, especially in the root, thus becomes the first point of sensing for decreased water potential. Importantly, this sensitivity is not limited to the root tissues themselves: the root-soil interface can act as a critical control point. In this region, Schuldt et al.⁴² emphasized the need to reconsider classical concepts of root xylem vulnerability (the “root-as-hydraulic-fuse” hypothesis). Their updated hypothesis proposes that hydraulic disconnection may instead originate at the root-soil interface, when the cortex shrinks during moderate soil drying, a situation commonly experienced by grapevines.

Another “fuse” for controlling embolism damage, one that grapevines can sacrifice relatively easily, has often been identified in the leaf, through a mechanism leading to petiole abscission. This idea is the basis of the hydraulic segmentation hypothesis, according to which cavitation occurs at less negative water potentials in the petiole than in the stem^{44–47}. Through this mechanism, the vine can tolerate substantial drops in water potential near the leaves. However, its effectiveness has recently been questioned by direct measurements in grapevine^{48,49}. Indeed, growing evidence indicates that measurement artifacts have historically overestimated embolism vulnerability, suggesting that plants may not experience severe drought-induced embolism events under natural field conditions^{33,42,50}. These considerations, now extended to all tree species, are supported by more than fifteen years of *in vivo* evidence collected by micro-CT technology across grapevine species and cultivars. In this field, *in situ* and *in vivo* demonstrations of intra- or inter-species-specific hydraulic tolerance factors during drought acclimation in grapevine is a benchmark of the literature on the subject^{51–61}.

Another interesting insight into the hydraulic regulation of stress tolerance arises from examining the interaction between hydraulic conductivity and hydraulic capacitance, the latter supplying water to the transpiration stream and buffering fluctuations in water potential. Vergenst et al.⁶² were able to establish vulnerability curves for *V. vinifera* L. ‘Johanniter’ and quantify hydraulic capacitance during dehydration. They demonstrated that, during cavitation, the loss of hydraulic conductivity was accompanied by a 22–92% increase in hydraulic capacitance, suggesting that vines can tolerate some degree of cavitation during drought episodes. Although this mechanism is underexplored, it is likely linked to the involvement of aquaporins in the regulation of both hydraulic capacitance and conductivity, at least in the leaf⁶³ (Fig. 3).

The grapevine biological platform manifests stress avoidance/tolerance mechanisms and drives biological interactions with grapevine’s microbiome

While *Arabidopsis* has been invaluable for advancing our understanding of gene functions and signalling pathways, several aspects of plant biology cannot be fully captured in this model. These limitations include, for example, the absence of arbuscular mycorrhizal (AM) symbiosis, the lack of certain specialized cell types, and differences in circadian regulation and

stress acclimation strategies. Woody species also present distinct challenges such as large genome size, transformation constraints and difficulties in defining orthologous genes due to evolutionary duplications or losses. Such discrepancies highlight the need for complementary models, with perennial species like grapevine offering insights that are inaccessible through *Arabidopsis* alone⁶⁴. Unlike annual model plants, grapevine exhibits a long life cycle, complex perennial physiology, and pronounced genotype-dependent plasticity. It must survive and maintain productivity under recurrent episodes of water limitation, integrating a suite of structural, physiological, metabolic, and molecular responses that balance short-term survival with long-term fitness, responses that are, in turn, influenced by the genotype of the grafted rootstock⁶⁵.

As mentioned above, stress-avoidance mechanisms in grapevine are primarily governed by hydraulic regulation and stomatal control. Grapevine genotypes span a *continuum* between isohydric and anisohydric behaviours, with isohydric cultivars maintaining tighter stomatal regulation to conserve water, whereas anisohydric cultivars sustain higher photosynthetic and gas exchange rates even as water potentials decline^{8,66,67}. This natural variability provides a powerful framework for identifying the genetic determinants of water-use efficiency and carbon balance under stress. In addition, structural traits such as deep root systems (shaped by the rootstock genotype), xylem anatomical features, and leaf morphological plasticity further contribute to the ability of grapevine to avoid passing critical thresholds of hydraulic failure during prolonged drought. For example, a study comparing rootstocks responses to water deficit has shown that drought not only reduces fine-root hydraulic conductivity and accelerates suberization but also reveals strong genotype-specific features. The drought-tolerant 110 R rootstock, for instance, maintains higher osmotic and hydrostatic conductivity, undergoes earlier yet more effective suberization, and sustains greater exosmotic water flow than the more sensitive 101-14Mgt genotype. These findings indicate that root anatomical and physiological adjustments are central to drought avoidance, and that their genotype-dependent variability provides valuable traits for screening and selecting drought-resilient rootstock-scion combinations⁶⁸. Stress-tolerance mechanisms, by contrast, enable grapevine to withstand and acclimate to low water availability once stress is established. These include osmotic adjustment via the accumulation of compatible solutes (such as proline, soluble sugars, and polyols) and the activation of antioxidant defence pathways that mitigate ROS accumulation^{69,70}. Transcriptomic and metabolomic analyses reveal that drought triggers extensive reprogramming of hormonal networks, including ABA, jasmonic acid, and ethylene, alongside the induction of secondary-metabolism pathways such as stilbene and flavonoid biosynthesis, which are particularly enriched in grapevine^{71–73}. These metabolic adjustments not only protect cellular integrity but also contribute to grapevine’s unique ability to fine-tune berry quality traits under water deficit, thereby linking stress tolerance with viticultural and oenological outcomes⁷.

Beyond the plant’s intrinsic traits, grapevine must also be considered as a holobiont, in which plant-associated microorganisms form an essential layer of stress resilience⁷⁴. The grapevine microbiome, comprising bacteria, fungi, viruses and archaea inhabiting roots, leaves, and berries, undergoes pronounced shifts under drought stress^{75,76}. Beneficial microbes, including for example *Bacillus*, *Acinetobacter*, *Pseudomonas*, and AM fungi (AMF), can promote drought resilience and growth by modulating hormonal signalling, enhancing nutrient uptake, and reprogramming gene expression in the host^{77,78}. AM symbiosis, in particular, improves carbon allocation and phosphorus acquisition while mitigating oxidative stress in grapevine roots exposed to drought^{79,80}. Rolli et al.⁷⁸ showed that root-associated bacterial communities across different grapevine rootstocks and cultivars support this view: selected strains with diverse plant growth-promoting traits can adhere to and colonize the rhizoplane, enhancing biomass accumulation, shoot growth, and photosynthetic performance under drought. Importantly, these beneficial effects were stress-dependent and were particularly pronounced in drought-sensitive genotypes, highlighting the microbiome as an active contributor to grapevine acclimation through the recruitment of

context-specific microbial functions. Mechanistically, beneficial microorganisms enhance grapevine resilience to water deficit in several ways. They fine-tune hormonal balances, for instance by reducing stress-induced ethylene through ACC deaminase activity, thereby sustaining root growth and water uptake under limiting conditions. They also promote the accumulation of compatible solutes such as proline and soluble sugars, strengthening osmotic adjustment, and enhancing antioxidant defences through the accumulation of superoxide dismutase, catalase, peroxidase and melatonin, which collectively mitigate oxidative damage. At the transcriptional level, microbial inoculation triggers a complex network of stress-responsive genes involved in ABA biosynthesis (e.g., *VvNCED1*), proline and sugar metabolism, and the phenylpropanoid pathway, while activating signalling cascades mediated by WRKY, MYB, and GRAS transcription factors. In addition, AMF have been shown to influence small RNA regulation (e.g., the miR156/miR529/miR535 superfamily) and secondary metabolism, stimulating the production of flavonoids and stilbenes with recognized antioxidant and protective functions⁸¹. Collectively, these findings underscore the importance of integrating plant–microbe interactions into grapevine drought acclimation studies: the microbiome is not merely a passive passenger but an active co-determinant of host stress responses.

The grapevine biological platform also provides opportunities to explore long-term acclimation strategies, including stress memory and transgenerational effects in woody crops. Evidence suggests that recurrent drought exposure can prime grapevine physiological and molecular responses, leading to faster or stronger activation of protective mechanisms upon subsequent stress events. Such stress imprinting may involve epigenetic modifications, metabolic reallocation, and shifts in microbiome composition that persist beyond a single stress episode. In particular, epigenetic mechanisms have emerged as major players contributing to the primed state of plants after stress exposure⁸². The study by Rodríguez-Izquierdo et al.⁸³, conducted on cultivated and wild accessions of *Vitis*, provides evidence of genome-wide differential methylation related to stress-response and metabolic pathways in *Vitis*. Other recent studies have also addressed the epigenetic adaptive capacities of vines in relation to different environments^{84–86}, under different possible stressors, as reviewed by Tan and Rodríguez López⁸⁷. Understanding how the processes underlying stress memory operate in grapevine could reveal new targets for enhancing resilience to abiotic stress^{88–90}. To do this, the scientific community should move beyond the numerous studies in the literature that analyse single events of water stress and recovery in grapevine, and instead focus on experimental trials involving repeated exposure to long-lasting water stress events, ideally over multiple years, capable of linking drought history, epigenome, transcriptome and phenotype. Pioneering studies are beginning to emerge, such as the adoption of a multidisciplinary approach (i.e. eco-physiological, anatomical, biochemical and molecular analyses) to characterize ‘Nebbiolo’ plants subjected to recurrent drought events over several years⁹¹. In the next section, some notes on the state of the art of multi-stress and multi-layer survey in viticulture will be addressed.

Without any doubt, grapevine embodies a highly integrative model where water stress avoidance and tolerance are closely intertwined with its perennial life strategy, genetic diversity, and microbial partnerships. By examining grapevine as a holobiont, it becomes possible to capture a more holistic view of drought acclimation that extends beyond the host genome.

This perspective highlights grapevine as a valuable woody model crop for uncovering mechanisms of drought acclimation, while at the same time generating insights with translational relevance for sustainable agriculture and climate-resilient viticulture. The integration of ecophysiology, molecular biology, and microbiome research will be pivotal to define strategies that enhance perennial crop performance under climate change. Future research should prioritize the dissection of multilayered interactions underlying grapevine resilience, combining host genomic responses with microbiome contributions. Multi-omics approaches, coupled with ecophysiological measurements, will be essential to identify key regulatory nodes of acclimation and validate their ecological significance under vineyard conditions, often exposed to multi-stress constraints. Ultimately,

adopting a holobiont perspective in breeding programmes also based on new plant breeding techniques (NPBTs) may enable the development of resilient cultivars capable of sustaining productivity under increasingly harsh environments, reinforcing the role of grapevine as a model for other woody crops. In an optimal view, future experimental design should be standardised to allow replication and harmonization of results. This can be achieved by standardizing *i*) core metrics (physiological: predawn and midday leaf water potential, gs–VPD curves, canopy/berry temperature, Infra Red thermography; biochemical and molecular: analyses of osmolytes, antioxidant enzymes, sentinel metabolites; transcriptome; methylome) and *ii*) guidelines for stress imposition (soil drying rate; stress event intensity/duration; VPD targets) (Fig. 4).

Can the response to water stress be a valid first approximation of the multi-stress situation to which vineyards are subjected?

Although *Vitis vinifera* was domesticated under Mediterranean conditions, the specific climatic signature of Mediterranean-type viticultural regions has rarely been articulated as a conceptual framework for stress biology. These landscapes are defined by prolonged summer drought, episodic heat waves, and high evaporative demand, frequently occurring on shallow, low-organic-matter, stone-rich soils that limit water storage and root exploration. Climate projections indicate that such areas will experience the strongest increases in water deficit globally, driven by rising temperatures, reduced precipitation during ripening, and increased atmospheric water demand, with Europe among the most at-risk viticultural regions⁹². In the Mediterranean basin, this manifests as declining soil moisture, which is expected to intensify as evapotranspiration increases with temperature⁹³. Together, these constraints set Mediterranean viticulture apart from other warm-climate systems, where water scarcity and heat stress are typically decoupled rather than chronically co-occurring.

Despite this specificity, among abiotic factors, experimental design in grapevine physiology has often treated heat and drought as separate stressors, even though the plant rarely encounters them independently in Mediterranean field conditions. This conceptual gap is notable because the combined stress phenotype is not additive: hydraulic failure may occur at high vapour pressure deficit even when soil moisture is not limiting⁹⁴, while berry transpiration rates, critical for sugar loading and ripening, accelerate under high temperature and low humidity⁹⁵. The result is a cascade of metabolic uncoupling, in which berry development becomes asynchronously regulated relative to whole-plant water status and carbon balance⁹⁶. These dynamics directly challenge long-held assumptions about ripening trajectories and reinforce that Mediterranean vineyards represent a physiological endpoint of multifactorial stress, rather than a simple warm-climate variant.

In this context, abscisic acid (ABA) emerges as a potential integrator of drought–heat perception and berry ripening. Multiple components of the ABA pathway respond distinctly to water deficit and elevated temperature, yet their joint dynamics remain poorly understood^{97,98}. Critically, only a single study has explicitly examined transcriptomic responses to combined drought and temperature in grapevine, underscoring that the molecular logic of stress integration is still unresolved⁹⁸. The same is true for jasmonic acid (JA) and other hormonal networks that respond to both water deficit and thermal stress, potentially modulating oxidative damage and metabolic trade-offs under multifactorial pressure⁹⁹.

This Mediterranean perspective has several important implications for how grapevine resilience should be studied and improved. First, it shifts the concept of drought tolerance away from a single, static trait and instead frames it as a dynamic process, in which vines continuously balance water use, heat dissipation, and berry developmental trajectories. Under Mediterranean conditions, this balance determines not only the maintenance of physiological function but also the timing and quality of ripening, which can vary markedly among genotypes exposed to elevated temperatures¹⁰⁰. Second, recognising that drought and heat stress rarely occur in isolation means that evaluating vines under single-stress conditions may lead to misleading

Fig. 4 | Schematic summary of the multi-layered investigative approaches underway aimed at optimizing grapevine responses to drought. This scheme summarizes three complementary layers of grapevine responses and improvement strategies. On the left, the root-associated microbiome enhances tolerance through multiple processes, including bacterial ACC deaminase activity that lowers stress-induced ethylene, while arbuscular mycorrhizal fungi (AMF) that mitigate oxidative stress, collectively sustaining ABA biosynthesis and activating stress-responsive transcriptional networks (e.g., WRKY, MYB, GRAS). These responses promote the accumulation of protective metabolites such as stilbenes, flavonols, phenylpropanoids, soluble sugars, and proline. In the centre, plant-intrinsic acclimation involves drought- and heat-induced modulation of secondary metabolism, including the

activation of the phenylpropanoid pathway (*VvCHS*, *VvUFGT*, *VvF3'5'H*, *VvOMT*), stilbene biosynthesis, and acyltransferase-driven anthocyanin acylation (*VvGAT1*, *VvSCP5*, *VvSCP31*), alongside cultivar-specific alterations in flavonol profiles. On the right, conventional breeding is constrained by the need to preserve historical cultivars, whereas New Plant Breeding Techniques (NPBTs) including genome editing can specifically target traits such as stomatal behaviour (*VvEPF9-1*, *OST2*, *GID1*), biochemical and hormonal responses (*VvGST40*, *VvbZIP36*, *ERA1*, *AREB1*, *TRE1*, *LBD*), and microbial recruitment (*VvNPR3*). This integrative view highlights how combining plant physiology, microbial symbioses, and biotechnology can advance sustainable viticulture under climate change.

conclusions. Genotypes identified as resilient under drought alone may fail when heat waves coincide with water scarcity, which represents the actual selective pressure faced in Mediterranean vineyards. Ignoring this simultaneity risks overlooking germplasm that is well adapted to real-world field conditions. Finally, framing viticulture through a Mediterranean lens offers a unifying conceptual structure. It connects environmental constraints, plant physiological responses, and berry metabolic outcomes into a coherent system, providing a basis for predictive approaches. This shift toward mechanistic integration is essential for forecasting cultivar performance, guiding the selection of resilient plant material, and ensuring the long-term sustainability of viticulture in a rapidly changing climate²³.

In this context, understanding how grapevines perceive, regulate, and ultimately adapt to water deficit becomes central, as drought responses constitute the physiological backbone upon which resilience to more complex Mediterranean stress scenarios is built.

Exploitable target genes in breeding approaches aimed at improving avoidance/tolerance to water stress

The viticultural agro-ecosystem is seriously impacted by climate-change-induced abiotic stresses and by the intensification of fungal diseases¹⁰¹. Grapevine cultivation relies heavily on plant protection products, mainly fungicides, and it has ecological impacts ascribable to soil compaction and loss of biodiversity, making the development of efficient approaches to genetic improvement absolutely urgent. Grapevine breeding presents peculiar challenges: while conventional breeding is commonly exploited for table grape genotypes, the introduction of new wine grape varieties is extremely difficult. This is mainly due to the fact that economically important and internationally renowned wine-grape genotypes constitute long-established vine-terroir combinations, and consumer choices strongly favour these historical varieties. The development of NPBTs offers a promising solution: the generation of improved genotypes that retain the original genome of the traditional variety, modified only for the desired trait¹⁰². Recently, DNA-free genome editing protocols have been established for various grapevine cultivars^{103–105}, including the recalcitrant-to-*in vitro*

regeneration Nebbiolo¹⁰⁶. These advances make it feasible to obtain new genotypes without integrating foreign DNA and thus opening new possibilities for targeted improvement while preserving the identity of historical wine grapes.

However, even with these powerful techniques, grapevine improvement remains challenging due to the difficulty of finding effective target genes. Tolerance to abiotic stresses is governed by complex genetic networks, often exhibiting pleiotropic effects and strongly influenced by genome-environment interactions¹⁰⁷. Encouraging indications are beginning to emerge in grapevine, informed by the growing knowledge of the above-described avoidance and tolerance mechanisms. For example, edited *V. vinifera* plants cv Sugraone knocked out for the gene *Epidermal Patterning Factor Like 9-1* (*VvEPF9-1*), encoding a peptide that induces stomata formation in vascular plants also known as STOMAGEN, showed reduced stomatal density with increased water use efficiency. This highlights stomatal anatomical features as promising breeding targets for climate-change resilient crops¹⁰⁸. Moreover, spray-induced gene silencing (SIGS) targeting a grape *Glutathione S-transferase* (*GST*) gene (*VvGST40*), performed on Chardonnay cuttings then subjected to drought/recovery experiments revealed increased resilience of *VvGST40*-silenced plants to severe drought. The improved physiological performances appear linked to elevated ABA levels, a more active antioxidant system, and cross talk between the ABA and strigolactone pathways¹⁰⁹. Furthermore, this work validates SIGS as a tool in grapevine for the rapid functional characterization of candidate genes then exploitable as targets in genome editing strategies. Interesting indications emerge also from the editing of the *VvNPR3* gene in Chardonnay, which led to improved tolerance to both *Erysiphe necator* and *Plasmopara viticola*¹¹⁰. The *Nonexpressor of Pathogenesis-Related* (*NPR*) gene family is a key regulator of the Systemic Acquired Resistance (SAR) responses orchestrated by salicylic acid. Specifically, *NPR3* is a negative regulator of SAR, and its editing enhances plant defence responses against biotic stresses. Importantly, because *VvNPR3* is not a susceptibility gene for a specific pathogen, but rather a repressor of general defence responses, these edited lines may also yield positive results if tested under abiotic stresses. Indeed, preliminary

analyses show that AMF recruiting is enhanced in *VvNPR3*-edited Chardonnay lines, with a positive impact on performances under drought¹¹¹.

Beyond grapevine-specific breeding approaches, several candidate genes identified in other species¹¹² could provide promising targets for improving water stress avoidance and tolerance in grapevine. For instance, the CRISPR/Cas9 system was successfully used in *Arabidopsis* to create novel alleles of *OPEN STOMATA 2 (OST2)*, a stomatal proton pump, and the resulting genome-edited lines displayed enhanced performances via altered stomatal closure under drought stress¹¹³. Another target acting at the stomatal level is the *ENHANCED RESPONSE TO ABA1 (ERA1)* gene, encoding the β -subunit of farnesyltransferase and regulating ABA signalling and dehydration responses. *era1* mutant plants showed enhanced ABA-induced stomatal closure, making it a promising candidate for increasing drought tolerance in a variety of crops¹¹⁴. A further promising target is again related to ABA signalling: the overexpression of *ABA-responsive element-binding protein 1 (AREB1)* improved *Arabidopsis* physiological performances under severe drought. This result was achieved by CRISPR activation (CRISPRa), a technique that could be potentially applied to other ABA-related genes for drought-targeted breeding strategies¹¹⁵. Targets outside the ABA pathway are also promising. In tomato, the editing of the *GIBBERELLIN-INSENSITIVE DWARF1 (GID1)* gibberellin receptor successfully reduced whole-plant transpiration under water-deficit conditions without impairing growth. Reduced gibberellin activity inhibited leaf growth, promoted stomatal closure, and reduced xylem vessel proliferation and expansion, therefore decreasing hydraulic conductivity and limiting water loss¹¹⁶. The jasmonate pathway also offers potential targets. The *LATERAL ORGAN BOUNDARIES DOMAIN (LBD)* transcription factors are plant-specific regulators of various processes, including organ development and response to stress. In tomato, *LBD40* expression is jasmonate-dependent and its CRISPR/Cas9 targeted mutagenesis improved drought tolerance by enhancing the water-holding capacity of the plant. Notably, grapevine is known to possess five *LBD* genes responsive to salt, mannitol, heat, and cold stresses¹¹⁷, making them promising candidates for genome editing aimed at multi-stress tolerance.

An interesting gene target for enhancing tolerance mechanisms in anisohydric grapevine varieties is related to the trehalose catabolic pathway, given the osmoprotective role of this metabolite. *Arabidopsis* gene-edited mutants of *TRE1*, which encodes the trehalase enzyme responsible for trehalose hydrolysis, exhibited enhanced drought tolerance¹¹⁸. Finally, the accumulation of anthocyanins, key metabolites that contribute both to grapevine berry quality and defence responses, is known to confer tolerance to various abiotic stresses in multiple plant species¹¹⁹. Under prolonged stomatal closure in the context of an avoidance strategy, ROS accumulate and act as signalling molecules that activate transcription of anthocyanin biosynthesis genes. The resulting anthocyanins then participate in antioxidant activities by scavenging excess ROS and thus helping maintain osmotic balance and increase abiotic stress tolerance. Engineering anthocyanin-enriched plants therefore represents a possible strategy for grapevine improvement, although careful evaluation of metabolite accumulation in berries will be essential. Genome-editing approaches targeting negative regulators of anthocyanin biosynthesis could also be exploited. For example, *VvbZIP36*-edited Thompson seedless grapevines with increased anthocyanin accumulation have already been generated, although their responses to abiotic stresses have not yet been characterized¹²⁰.

Despite the application of powerful techniques such as NPBTs for grapevine breeding, field testing remains an essential final step to assess the success of the strategy. Only under real vineyard conditions can agronomical and oenological performances, environmental adaptation, and possible pleiotropic effects be evaluated. This need arises not only because the genes regulating abiotic stress responses often participate in other developmental processes, but also because constitutive enhancement of defence mechanisms may impact on the growth-defence trade-off. Moreover, given the strong interconnection between defence responses to abiotic and biotic stresses, such as the shared reliance on the ABA pathway, it is advisable to assess the new genotypes for multi-stress tolerance. Finally, it is worth

noting that achieving resilient viticulture will require coupling the new genotypes with effective vineyard management and Integrated Pest Management (IPM) strategies (Fig. 4).

Do drought acclimation mechanisms impact strategic agricultural issues and pathogen defence mechanisms of the vine?

There is a long history of agronomic practices that have been proposed to address water stress, developed and adopted especially in the Mediterranean environment, where water stress is accompanied by combined thermal and radiative stress^{1,92-94}.

Many systematic agronomical approaches and field practices might decrease water deficit effect in viticulture, allowing grapevines to maintain their optimal qualitative traits. Among the systematic agronomical approaches that foresee a medium-long time window are some Nature-Based Solutions (NBS) in viticulture such as the return to consociation, that is growing vines with other trees, whose primary goal is limiting the negative effect of excessive exposure to UV-rays and impairments to photosystems, leading to photoxidation. In this sense, the ancient and Latin-Mediterranean “*vitis maritae*”, today renamed “viti-forestry”, could represent a useful mean to the contribution of viticulture to agro-forest ecosystems services. Also, avoiding establishing new monoculture areas of cultivation and the use of land with diversified herbaceous inter-cultivation are options implying a different use of the water resource and a possible acclimation strategy to new environmental traits. Cover-cropping, organic amendments, new cultivars and/or the recovery of ancient cultivars represent the basic solutions for adapting viticulture to water scarcity.

In the short-medium time, in current viticultural systems, some field practices have shown their potentiality in helping grapevines to overcome water deficits, as recently reviewed by Reta and co-workers¹²¹. Among green pruning operations, basal leaf removal plays a direct role in regulating vine water availability and WUE and many studies demonstrated the necessity to maintain an optimal balance between canopy development and crop load. The time of intervention is of primary importance: late leaf removal (since around véraison onwards) is a useful operation to improve the vine water status and the photosynthetic rate but the expected effects on sugar reduction are limited, whereas some negative effects may occur in relation to the accumulation of colour^{122,123}. Early leaf removal (for instance at the stage of pepper corn size) has no impact on the seasonal leaf water potential of vines, on acid and sugar concentrations but it displays a profound impact on berry carotenoid (xanthophylls) concentrations, that increase, with consequent high concentrations of norisoprenoids and of monoterpenes at harvest¹²⁴.

Insights of the influence of training system choice have highlighted that some training systems such as the Mediterranean-traditional gobelet and the new proposed Y-shaped training systems, help grapevines to promote efficient water use, particularly through the reduction of the canopy development the first (reduced leaf area index reduces plant evapotranspiration) and by favouring leaf and bunch shading, the second.

Direct or indirect control of low soil water availability (through practices such as regulated deficit irrigation, partial root-drying, or modulation of soil texture) allows grapevine to optimize berry qualitative traits in a cultivar- × rootstock- × environment- × season-dependent manner. As described above, drought acclimation in grapevine encompasses a wide range of possible mechanisms, from modifications in xylem vessel morphology, number, and dimensions to the accumulation of osmolytes, all of which contribute both to berry quality definition and to responses against pathogens¹²⁵.

In drought-acclimated cultivated grapevines, key genes of the phenylpropanoid pathway are overexpressed, such as *Chalcone synthase (CHS)*, *UDP glucose: flavonoid-3-O-glucosyltransferase (UFGT)*, *Flavonoid 3',5'-hydroxylase (F3'5'H)* and *Ortho-methyl-transferase (OMT)*^{71,126}. This upregulation alters anthocyanin profiles in the berry through the accumulation of tri-hydroxylated and methylated forms, and increases total anthocyanin content. Rising average temperature and more frequent heatwaves above the

35 °C threshold, conditions often associated with drought, further promote anthocyanin acylation^{127,128}. However, knowledge about acyltransferase in grapevine remains limited. Although *BAHD-AT*²⁹, *VvGAT1*, *VvSCP5* and *VvSCP31*¹³⁰ have been identified as candidate acyltransferase-encoding genes involved in anthocyanin acylation, no functional studies have yet demonstrated their direct regulation by water availability or relation to the degree of drought adaptation in specific genotypes. Increasing anthocyanin molecular weight through tri-hydroxylation, methylation and acylation leads to variations in must and wine colour and influences wine stability during aging. The fine chemical analyses of individual polyphenols further reveal that many phenylpropanoid accumulation patterns are cultivar-specific, and thus, clearly under strong genetic control. For instance, the combination of high temperatures and drought has been shown to increase concentration, methylation, and acylation of anthocyanins in Tempranillo and Cabernet Sauvignon berries, but to cause only limited variations in Merlot and Grenache¹³¹, and no detectable change in Shiraz¹³². Beyond these clear genotype-dependent responses, cultivar adaptation to local environmental conditions, soils and cultural practices leads the same genotype to display distinct accumulation patterns of specific compounds. Such environmentally driven metabolic variation allows the production and definition of 'Terroir' wines. Two examples illustrate this point. First, the polyphenolic profiles of mature berries from a single Corvina clone collected across seven vineyards within the same vintage clearly separated the three macro-zones of origin, with peonidin-3-O-glucoside and acylated anthocyanins emerging as markers of berry provenance¹³³. Second, the volatile organic compound (VOC) profiles of berries from own-rooted, non-irrigated Xynisteri vines grown in two different cultivation areas displayed notable variations at full ripeness, particularly in glycosylated monoterpenes and benzenic compounds; these metabolites are known to serve as key 'flavour reservoir' in wines¹³⁴. In that study, factors such as adequate soil calcium availability, high clay content, low precipitation associated with elevated mean temperature, including a substantial number of days exceeding 35 °C, were associated with shifts in VOC concentration and profiles. In line with these observations, research has demonstrated that the distribution of JA and/or its derivatives, or the adoption of practices that increase endogenous JA, such as water deprivation before véraison¹³⁵, increases the concentration of glycosylated monoterpenes, with potential implications for the aromatic quality of future wines.

Chemical and enzymatic degradation patterns of secondary metabolites also reflect grapevine adaptation to drought. The enzymatic breakdown of anthocyanins depends on the constitutive polyphenolic composition of the cultivar, which itself is shaped by water availability during berry development and is exacerbated under drought. Berries grown under water deficit tend to be richer in methylated and acylated anthocyanins, which are less prone to degradation than non-methylated and non-acylated forms¹³⁶. During the last stages of ripening, breakdown products such as dimers, flavanol-ethyl anthocyanins, hydroxyphenyl- and catechyl-pyranoanthocyanins form within the berry. Their molecular structures, type and relative abundance are strongly influenced by vine water status¹³³, and their concentrations and profile significantly impact colour intensity and persistency in wines.

Flavonol concentrations in berries and vegetative organs are mainly associated with grapevine responses to light. However, Pascual and co-workers¹³¹ recently demonstrated that the combination of heat and drought reduced berry concentrations of di-hydroxylated flavonols, particularly of quercetin 3-O-glucoside, typically the predominant flavonol in berry skins. Previous research highlighted that water stress increases must flavonol concentration in a cultivar-dependent manner^{132,137}. Flavonols are important co-pigments in must and young red wines¹³⁸, and quercetin 3-O-glucoside, in particular, is associated with the formation of long-lasting copigments in wines¹³⁹.

Grapevine capability to activate immune defences also relies on the accumulation of specific secondary metabolites across different organs (berries, leaves, stems, wood, roots). Drought, by altering gene expression and metabolite accumulation in an organ-specific manner, can boost the

vine potential to fend off pathogens. In addition to stilbenoids, long recognized for their role in immunity^{140,141}, other polyphenols can directly restrict pathogen development. For example, high amounts of leaf flavonols slow tissue colonization by *Plasmopara viticola*¹⁴², and the leaf polyphenolic content, particularly quercetin and kaempferol 3-O-glucosides, correlates strongly with moderate to severe water stress¹⁴³. Thus, drought could strengthen the vine immune system both directly, through the synthesis of protective metabolites, and indirectly, by reducing canopy vigour. The resulting increase in leaf exposure to sunlight increases leaf flavonol accumulation, decreasing infection susceptibility.

In the interaction between grapevine and the Flavescence dorée phytoplasma, the enhancement of the phenylpropanoid pathway¹⁴⁴, the induction of a stress-memory signal through the overexpression of stilbene-synthases and increased DNA methylation in recovered plants¹⁴⁵, represent a metabolic pattern strikingly similar to that observed under drought. This parallel suggests that prior drought exposure could increase the grapevine defence capabilities against pathogens, especially if stress-memory is confirmed. Marfil and collaborators¹⁴⁶ described unstable epigenetic signatures and/or stochastic drought-induced changes in DNA-methylation; nevertheless, they also found significantly higher concentrations of hydroxycinnamic acids (caftaric and p-coumaric acids) in fertile shoots developing in the season following a drought event. This suggests that drought-induced DNA methylation could regulate the accumulation of specific polyphenolic compounds participating in grapevine acclimation and susceptibility to pathogens. Overall, drought acclimation in grapevine, besides influencing hydraulic, stomatal and photosynthetic regulation, also alters the concentrations of gamma-amino butyric acid (GABA) in stressed cells. GABA functions as a priming agent enabling faster physiological adjustment to stress, mainly through ABA accumulation. Furthermore, GABA has been implicated in potential intergenerational priming mechanisms, contributing long-term drought resilience in grapevine⁸⁸.

Taken together, these observations reinforce that ABA-mediated water relations remain central to viticulture adaptation to climate change, shaping grapevine resilience, tolerance to both biotic and abiotic stressors, and ultimately the optimization of berry quality⁷ (Fig. 4).

Conclusions and open questions

Grapevine represents a unique biological platform for unravelling drought acclimation strategies, integrating stress avoidance and tolerance mechanisms with perennial growth habits, grafting dynamics, and strong genotype-dependent plasticity. The evidence discussed here underscores how physiological traits, hormonal signalling, secondary metabolism, and microbial partnerships collectively shape plant responses to fluctuating water availability (Fig. 3). Yet, despite substantial advances, our understanding remains fragmented, and several critical challenges must be addressed to fully exploit grapevine as a model for perennial crop resilience.

A first limitation concerns the integration of ecophysiological and molecular processes into predictive frameworks. While the distinction between isohydric and anisohydric behaviours provides a useful conceptual scaffold, most genotypes display intermediate, dynamic strategies modulated by environment, soil texture, and rootstock-scion combinations. Systematic efforts to link stomatal control, xylem hydraulics, osmotic regulation, and whole-plant carbon balance under realistic vineyard conditions are still lacking. In this regard, multi-scale modelling coupled with long-term field trials will be required to clarify whether theoretical definitions of avoidance and tolerance can be effectively translated into actionable selection criteria for breeding and management.

Second, the role of secondary metabolism in shaping both berry quality and stress defence remains incompletely resolved. While anthocyanin decoration, stilbene accumulation, and flavonol dynamics are clearly linked to drought and heat stress, their cultivar-specific patterns, organ-level variability, and interactions with pathogen resistance require deeper functional analysis. Genes encoding acyltransferases, transcriptional regulators,

and ABA- or JA-dependent pathways emerge as promising candidates, but only a few have been validated under fluctuating field conditions. This knowledge gap limits the use of NPBTs for climate resilience without risking pleiotropic or undesirable effects on wine typicity.

Third, the grapevine microbiome, encompassing root-associated bacteria, fungi, and viruses, has emerged as an active determinant of stress acclimation with the ability to modulate hormonal balances, antioxidant defences, and osmotic adjustment, particularly in drought-sensitive genotypes. However, microbial contributions are highly context-dependent, and robust strategies to integrate microbiome-mediated resilience into viticultural practice are still lacking. Advancing this field will require combining metagenomics, transcriptomics, and metabolomics with vineyard-scale inoculation trials to translate the microbiome potential into reproducible outcomes.

Finally, stress memory and epigenetic regulation, though increasingly recognized as pivotal in the acclimation of perennial species, remain poorly characterized in grapevine. Preliminary evidence suggests that drought can induce shifts in DNA methylation and transgenerational priming of polyphenolic metabolism, but the molecular underpinnings and ecological relevance of these phenomena are still largely speculative. Clarifying how memory and holobiont dynamics intersect could open new avenues for breeding and for designing more sustainable vineyard systems.

Altogether, grapevine offers an unparalleled opportunity to bridge physiology, molecular genetics, and agroecology in the study of drought resilience (Fig. 4). Future research should prioritize integrative, multi-omics approaches embedded in realistic vineyard contexts, explicitly considering multi-stress scenarios in which drought co-occurs with heatwaves and pathogen pressure. Adopting a holobiont-centred and long-term perspective will not only refine our understanding of grapevine acclimation but also provide transferable insights for other woody crops, reinforcing viticulture's leading role at the forefront of climate-smart agriculture.

Received: 2 October 2025; Accepted: 24 March 2026;

Published online: 03 June 2026

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Acknowledgements

C.L. gratefully acknowledges the funding by PE9 GRINS financed by the Next Generation EU programme in the frame of the SPOKE 6 – WP1 activity, grant agreement no. PE0000018 - CUP D13C22002160001. Part of the work was carried out within the project “Shield4Grape: Breeding and integrated pest management strategies to reduce reliance on chemical pesticides in grapevine,” funded by the European Union through the Horizon Europe Research and Innovation Programme (Grant number 101135088). Views and opinions expressed are, however, those of the authors only. Neither the European Union nor the granting authority nor the European Commission can be held responsible for them. Figures 3 and 4 have been created in BioRender (<https://BioRender.com/d0p101y> and <https://BioRender.com/959m1on>).

Author contributions

I.P., W.C., L.N. and A.F. wrote and revised the manuscript and prepared the figures coordinated by C.L. who theorized the structure of the perspective. All authors read and approved the manuscript.

Competing interests

The authors declare no competing interests.

Additional information

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